

A Case Study: Teachers Education Program in a Global Context

Authors : In Hoi Lee, Seong Baeg Kim, Je Eung Jeon, Gwang Yong Choi, Joo Sub Lee, Ik Sang Kim

Abstract : Recently, the interest of globalization in the field of teacher education has increased. In the U.S., the government is trying to enhance the quality of education through a global approach in education. To do so, the schools in the U.S. are recruiting teachers with global capability from countries like Korea where competent teachers are being trained. Meanwhile, in the case of Korea, although excellent teachers have been cultivated every year, due to a low birth rate it is not easy to become a domestic teacher. To solve the trouble that the two countries are facing, the study first examines the demand and necessity of globalization in the field of teacher education between Korea and the U.S. Second, we propose a new project, called the 'Global Teachers University (GTU)' program to satisfy the demands of both countries. Finally, we provide its implications to build the future educational cooperation for teacher training in a global context.

Keywords : educational cooperation, globalization, teachers education program, teacher training institutions

Conference Title : ICELET 2014 : International Conference on e-Learning and e-Teaching

Conference Location : Zurich, Switzerland

Conference Dates : January 14-15, 2014